

EFFECT OF DEXTRAN AND STARCH DERIVATIVES ON PLATELET AGGREGATION IN CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES

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Abstract. *This article demonstrates that the antiplatelet activity of dextran derivatives (D-38) and starch derivatives (K-39) on the plasma of patients with cardiovascular diseases is more effective than acetylsalicylic acid and clopidogrel.*

Keywords: *dextran sulfate (D-38), starch sulfate (K-39), acetylsalicylic acid, hypertension, coronary artery disease, hemostasis, clopidogrel, heparin.*

INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular diseases remain the leading cause of mortality worldwide. The development of these diseases is due to atherosclerotic damage to blood vessels, increased blood coagulation, arterial thrombosis, platelet aggregation, and disturbances in coagulation hemostasis. Currently, patients with cardiovascular diseases are recommended to use drugs with anticoagulant and antiplatelet activities [1,2,3]. The use of some anticoagulants and antiplatelet agents can cause side effects. For example, prolonged use of heparin carries a high risk of thrombocytopenia. At the same time, it is important to study the mechanisms of action of sulfated polysaccharides on platelet activation and their aggregation activity. Studying the effectiveness of new natural compounds with anticoagulant and antiplatelet properties in the prevention and treatment of thrombosis complications is one of the current problems in medicine.

Research Objective: In vitro study of the effect of dextran derivatives (D-38) and starch derivatives (K-39) on platelet activity in patients with cardiovascular diseases.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For studying platelet aggregation, blood taken from patients (140 people) with cardiovascular diseases (hypertension, coronary artery disease) was mixed with a 3.8% sodium citrate solution in a ratio of 9:1 and centrifuged at a speed of 1000g for 10 minutes (Rotor centrifuge OPN-8 RU180 L, 2000 g) [5]. The Born method, based on registering changes in the light transmittance of platelet-rich plasma, and the process of aggregate formation are graphically displayed, expressed as a percentage of the light transmittance level (T%, max), caused by random changes in the number of platelet aggregation particles (C/Φ5027358/1 from 11.03.2021 Biola, Russia), which were determined using an aggregometer [6-7]. The following inducers of platelet aggregation were used: ADP (5-10 μM), adrenaline (5 μM), collagen (0.2 U/ml), and ristocetin (0.6 U/ml) ("Sigma"). Our experiments were based on the International ethical principles for biomedical research involving human subjects (CIOMS 2016).

Data obtained during the experiments were processed statistically. Data processing and figure preparation were carried out using the computer program Origin 7.1 (Microsoft, USA). For comparing independent samples that follow a normal distribution, we used the parametric Student's t-test. The t-test values were calculated for a 95% significance level ($p \leq 0.05$). Histograms show the means and their standard errors from 3-5 independent experiments.

RESULTS AND THEIR ANALYSIS

In our experiments, we evaluated the effect of D-38 and K-39 derivatives on platelet aggregation in plasma. Although it is known that the above inducers affect platelet function, their repeated values in studies assessing platelet activity need to be determined depending on the apparatus and reagents. Therefore, we studied in vitro the effect of ADP, adrenaline, collagen, and ristocetin inducers on platelet functional activity in plasma from healthy individuals and patients with cardiovascular diseases. It is known that platelet aggregation was observed upon exposure to such inducers as ADP, adrenaline, collagen, and ristocetin in healthy human platelets.

When ADP was added to platelets in plasma from patients, aggregation occurred at a concentration of $5 \mu\text{M}$, initially in a single-phase manner, and at a higher concentration of $10 \mu\text{M}$, irreversible secondary aggregation of platelets was observed in a two-phase curve. The ADP inducer acts on platelet P2Y receptors, which are coupled with γ -protein, seven-transmembrane-domain receptors (P2Y1 and P2Y12). The P2Y1 receptors mobilize intracellular calcium ions to mediate platelet shape change and aggregation [7,8]. It was found that P2Y12 receptors inhibit adenylate cyclase through γ -protein [9].

Figure 1. The effect of D-38 and K-39 derivatives on ADP-induced platelet aggregation in coronary artery disease (A) and hypertension (B). *- $p < 0.05$; ** - $p < 0.01$. ($n=6$).

When studying the effect of D-38 and K-39 derivatives in plasma from patients with coronary artery disease and hypertension at a concentration of $50 \mu\text{L}$ on aggregation induced by ADP ($10 \mu\text{M}$), the compounds reduced the aggregation level by 25-30% compared to the control in coronary artery disease, 10-15% compared to aspirin, and 20-25% compared to clopidogrel. In hypertension, the level of aggregation decreased by 30-40% compared to the control, by 15-25% compared to aspirin, and by 25-35% compared to clopidogrel. From this, we conclude that D-38 and K-39 derivatives, at a concentration of $50 \mu\text{L}$ in patients with cardiovascular diseases, act on P2Y1 and P2Y12 receptors in platelet plasma, reducing thromboxane A₂ formation, activating adenylate cyclase, and reducing platelet aggregation by inhibiting Ca²⁺ release from the cell (Figure 1).

In further studies, we exposed plasma from patients to collagen inducer at a concentration of 0.2 mg/ml and induced platelet aggregation. Endothelial cells inhibit the interaction of circulating platelets with various types of collagen present in the subendothelial matrix [10]. The platelet GPVI receptor interacts with collagen, leading to platelet activation.

Figure 2. The effect of D-38 and K-39 derivatives on collagen-induced platelet aggregation in coronary artery disease (A) and hypertension (B). *- $p < 0.05$; **- $p < 0.01$. ($n=6$).

When studying the effect of D-38 and K-39 derivatives in plasma from patients with coronary artery disease and hypertension at a concentration of 50 μ L on aggregation induced by collagen (0.2 mg/ml), the compounds reduced the level of aggregation compared to the control in coronary artery disease by 28-30%, compared to aspirin by 20-18%, and compared to clopidogrel by 20-23%. In hypertension, the level of aggregation decreased by 35-40% compared to the control, by 22-27% compared to aspirin, and by 25-30% compared to clopidogrel. We conclude that D-38 and K-39 derivatives at a concentration of 50 μ L affect the binding of the GPVI receptor on plasma platelets with collagen, prevent platelet adhesion to the endothelium, and consequently reduce platelet aggregation (Figure 2).

Subsequent studies involved the aggregation of platelets upon exposure to plasma from patients to adrenaline inducer at concentrations of 2-5 μ mol. Adrenaline at a concentration of 5 μ mol caused aggregation in the form of a two-phase curve, and at higher concentrations, it induced irreversible platelet aggregation. Adrenaline interacts with α 2-adrenergic receptors on the platelet membrane, significantly inhibiting the adenylate cyclase enzyme, stimulating thromboxane A2 production, increasing membrane permeability, and ion calcium transport [13]. As a result of these inducers, the concentration of calcium in the cell cytosol increases, leading to phosphorylation of platelet proteins. A sharp increase in the concentration of Ca^{2+} in the endoplasmic reticulum plays a crucial role in platelet activation, including the release of aggregation and coagulation factors. The primary element of platelet activation is the release of calcium ions from intracellular depots, leading to platelet aggregation [12].

When studying the effect of D-38 and K-39 derivatives in plasma from patients with coronary artery disease and hypertension at a concentration of 50 μ L on aggregation induced by adrenaline (5 μ M), the compounds reduced the level of aggregation compared to the control in coronary artery disease by 20-25%, compared to aspirin by 5-10%, and compared to clopidogrel by 10-15%. In hypertension, the level of aggregation decreased by 40-45% compared to the control, by 30-35% compared to aspirin, and by 25-35% compared to clopidogrel. The mechanism of action of D-38 (50 μ L) and K-39 (50 μ L) on platelet aggregation induced by adrenaline at a concentration of 5 μ M in patients with cardiovascular diseases is based on adenylate cyclase

activation, reduced thromboxane A2 production, and decreased release of intracellular calcium ions. As a result, platelet aggregation decreases.

Figure 3. The effect of D-38 and K-39 derivatives on adrenaline-induced platelet aggregation in coronary artery disease (A) and hypertension (B). *- $p < 0.05$; ** - $p < 0.01$. (n=6).

Conclusions

1. Dextran and starch derivatives can be recommended for use in medicine and pharmaceuticals as safe antiplatelet and anticoagulant drugs.
2. When studying the effect of D-38 and K-39 derivatives on platelet aggregation in cardiovascular diseases (coronary artery disease, hypertension), it was found that they have a more effective impact in hypertension compared to coronary artery disease.
3. It was established that D-38 and K-39 derivatives have a stronger effect on platelet aggregation induced by ADP, adrenaline, and collagen than acetylsalicylic acid and clopidogrel, due to their impact on glycoprotein receptors on the platelet membrane in plasma from patients.

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